

HOW TO AVOID PLAGIARISM IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS BASED ON COMPUTER APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

The Project “How to Avoid Plagiarism at M. Phil Level” reflects various short comings of the students in attempting academic writing, reasons to indulge in plagiarism intentionally or un intentionally. Students of Education departments of all public and private universities of Multan City were the population of study. The population belonged to Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan, Institute of Southern Punjab Multan, Women University, Allama Iqbal University Multan (Students form Multan city only) and NCBA &E(Old 2017 Students). A sample of 45 students was taken through convenient sampling taking 9 students from each university. Questionnaire comprising of 20 items was distributed to these students through direct meeting with them, by E-mail and by Whats App.,in response but only 43 complete questionnaire were received. The return rate was 96 %.Four research questioned were answered with the help of questionnaire based on the data collected. It is recommended that Booklets on Plagiarism are available at HEC website these must be included in the teaching content i.e syllabus so that students may learn it during course work, there must be more emphasis on University plagiarism policy. The students must join direct and on-line courses, Seminars, conferences, student’s debates, Workshops and sessions with the experienced faculty members must be made to generate awareness about plagiarism. Academic writing practice sessions must be arranged on regular basis to improve poor language skills. Students must devote ample time for literature review. This will improve their paraphrasing skills, summarising skills, Lack of in-text referencing and weak citation.

INTRODUCTION

The term “Plagiarism” is often used by teachers and research assistants at university level. When someone says “ Don’t present a plagiarized work” . He actually means to say that one must do his/ her work with proper reference (Spiteri, 2007). The reference means way through which researcher can produce evidences (Grandy, 1973). It also means to admit

and acknowledge the work of the original author for his, idea, data, pictorial scenario and his effort (Spiteri, 2007). Plagiarism is sober activity, it is very severe violation by making copy of somebody's work (Chapman, et al., 1992). This word has Latin roots from word plagiarius, which means an abductor or kidnaper, and plagiare is used for stealing

(Chapman, et al., 1992). This Shortcut way of copying is very serious issue, but students are unaware of its consequences (Ehrich, 2016). Shah along with his co researchers described the followings cases of the plagiarism; Self-Plagiarism, Lack of in-text referencing, Single source plagiarism (Copy-paste one form), Multiple source plagiarism (Copy-paste another form), paraphrasing the original source and use of quotations (Shah, 2021). Jameson along with his team (2008) had initially grabbed attention regarding types of plagiarism. Every university tries to maintain the quality culture (Wang, 2025). A university expects from a researcher that he / she will learn or tend to learn from the original ideas of the great authors and the research professionals develop their own ideas having newness (Learning, 2010). Adam, Anderson and Spronken-Smith (2017) in their research relate the fact that plagiarism policy of the university builds students capacity for awareness, plagiarism understanding, and academic writing which is better than penalizing the students. Students must be clear about deliberate cheating and the unintentional plagiarism (Allagher, 2025). Some reason for academic theft are; Lack of plagiarism awareness, Heavy work Loads, Flexibility in the policy of the higher education institutions, Poor academic writing skill, Less knowledge of language, weak grammar, lack of paraphrasing skills and using culture of copy-paste form the published content (Ehrich, 2016). On the basis of their research and in the light of plagiarism policy introduced by university which was relabelled as Academic Integrity Policy. Suggestions were as follows; Provision of Clear information on plagiarism for students, suitable initiatives and environment availability for university teachers and students to improve the good academic practices, avoidance from penalizing or punishment for unethical act of plagiarism by students, develop the quality culture the university plagiarism policy as it is ongoing process there should be a system to review and implement plagiarism policy on the regular basis, System must be capable to address confusion of students (Adam, Anderson, & Spronken-Smith, 2017). Problem of plagiarism have now become global issue (Dimitrova, 2025). One may lose his job and spoil his carrier if he is found indulged in plagiarism (Taylor, 2025). Many other types of the

penalties are there if academic misconduct is proved. So, it is important to make researchers fully aware of the present scenario and the prevailing situation (Wu, 2025).

Statement of the Problem

The work presented here by researcher is about plagiarism and methods to avoid plagiarism at M. Phil level in Multan (Pakistan). The main objective of the study is to instigate to which extent the students are aware of plagiarism, the factors which force students to commit plagiarism intentionally or unintentionally and methods to avoid plagiarism in university at M. Phil Level. This survey study continued for a period of 04 weeks in public and private universities of Multan (Punjab) Pakistan.

Significance of the study

The problem addressed in this study was very crucial and was the need of the time (Kampa, 2025). We are in the age of science new ideas are replacing the conventional ideas. with the emergence of new technology, the access to data and literature have become easier (Chapman, et al., 1992). Students use copy past technique due to lack of time, over loaded syllabus or due to some other reason (Ehrich, 2016). This study is very important to know the root causes of plagiarism, its awareness among the students and methods to avoid plagiarism (Mahmud, 2013). This study will be helpful for creating awareness of plagiarism among the faculty members, students and the stake holders of the university to know about plagiarism (Chapman, et al., 1992). Teacher can improve the academic writing skill of the students in the light of findings of this research. Students can benefit from this study and can use the suggestions of the study to avoid plagiarism, all its cases and forms (Shah, 2021).

Rationale of the study

This study is very important, as this study tries to find the gap between previous studies and present scenario. This study will be helpful for creating awareness of plagiarism among the faculty members, students and the stake holders of the university to know about plagiarism. Teacher can play their role to improve the academic writing skill of the students in the light of findings of this research. This study will

be helpful for students in minimizing their fear regarding plagiarism.

Delimitations of the study

This study is constrained to only students belonging to education departments of universities in Multan.

Literature Review

The problem of plagiarism and how to avoid it have become an important issue internationally. Like other countries, valuable plagiarism awareness work is added in recent years by Taiwan scholars in the context of English as a foreign language (EFL). This work has helped a lot in investigation of plagiarism and measures to avoid plagiarism (Liu, 2018). Online tutorial system is introduced, even the instructional work done in this respect is very little but very effective to resolve plagiarism concerns for Taiwan research students. To come back and support this study Blended English Composition (BEC) course was employed along with the practical skill of writing tutorial system (Liu, 2018).

Outcomes of this study showed by instruction of explicit writing following advantages can be taken.

1. Capacity building of students to develop skills and knowledge with enhanced awareness of plagiarism
2. Strengthening the writing skill of scholars with accurate citation, and paraphrasing skill without change in actual meaning of the text.
3. Smart use of D Wright (Software) and Blended English writing instruction, to enable scholar so that they detect the magnitude of the similarity index.
4. Above discussed strategies will increase confidence of the scholars to counter the unintentional piracy.

Blended Language Learning (BLL) can help to narrow the down the literature and proper source usage can be made better than ever before (Liu, 2018).

Researchers who learned the overseas academic learning in comparison to those who did not learn the overseas academic learning of researchers belonging to different educational backgrounds were

examined, it was found that the researchers who invested their time in learning the overseas academic learning had developed more plagiarism awareness as others (Lei, 2015). Rezanejad (2013) used trial and error method to know implantation and awareness about plagiarism policy among TEFL Students, trainers and coaches in universities of Iran. Results indicated that knowledge of content of syllabus had lack in knowledge on plagiarism, its avoidance and penalties in case of his ethical activity. There is a great impact of culture on academic activities (Bikowski, 2018). Chinese culture still accepts the plagiarism to some extent due to language barrier and research also suggests "Warning about plagiarism is better than punishment" (Lei, 2015).

Use of soft wares to detect and avoid plagiarism

Plagiarism policy of the university or the institution plays a major role in establishing the in this research searcher shares findings (Allagher, 2025). Research reveals that (60%) of the respondents have claimed that the plagiarism was neither shared with them nor the policy explained to them at any education level during their course of study. This the policy about the intellectual theft is not established. This is also indicator of the educational priorities that the institution has not given any importance to the plagiarism policy (Starovoytova, 2017). University staff are given special accounts from where staff members can get plagiarism information of similarity index through Information retrieval (IR-Based) technique Which detects very accurate similarity index and it helps to find mis match index with high accuracy with great efficiency (Karnalim, 2018). Financial implication and ranking of the university is also responsible for implementation of plagiarism policy (Starovoytova, 2017). Course designed for instructors can fix priorities in their syllabus, for instance if ghost writing issue awareness is given prime importance then students will follow the university policy and avoid academic dishonesty (Starovoytova, 2017). Intellectual theft can result in falsify the reputation of author and there will be fear of sanctions for student (Jameson, et al., 2008)

Some useful measures to check Plagiarism (Frame work)

Followings are the recommendations;

Level	wise	Measures to be taken to stop plagiarism
Steps for at Global level		A centralized system should be made which contain the names of persons, Journals and institutions who were black listed for their intellectual theft.
Steps at National level		There is need of central scrutiny and observation system to check quality level of articles and publications of both public and private sector universities.
Steps at University Level		There should be provision of published content regarding plagiarism policy of university-on-university website, university admin, libraries, Chairmen of departments, research centres, study corners, photostat points and stationery shops for students' awareness.

(Starovoytova, 2017).

Plagiarism controlling strategies

Students give less importance to research and more to course work for getting good scores and grades in exams. (Jenkins, Bugeja, & Barber, 2014). Some students in spite of awareness about plagiarism use unethical writing to meet deadlines and tasks announce by university (Parkes, 2010). It is mandatory duty of the higher education institutions to provide comprehensive syllabus with awareness about plagiarism (Learning, 2010). Good academic practice is to include proper list practices along with the list of offences and penalties (Weber-Wulff, 2014).

Some measures which may be taken in this respect are

1. University students, admins, teachers and heads should be aware of plagiarism and student should submit antiplagiarism statement while submission of his publication (Weber-Wulff, 2014).
2. Clear cut plagiarism policy, assessment of projects under examination environment, practice of true citation, workshops for academic writing,

Paraphrasing skill development, inclusion of bio ethics and research ethics in syllabus could help in Quality dissertations (Jameson, et al., 2008).

Mahmud (2013) provided some themes in for universities to handle plagiarism issue; Recognize and appreciate the students and faculty members who show academic integrity to university policy, Arrange workshops, seminars, conferences and debates, for plagiarism awareness, start free online classes for training skills like summarizing, skimming, paraphrasing, citation and research ethics, The system should be there to treat with the document holding plagiarism, submitted content should be recorded properly, planned anti-plagiarism system should be activated to check the problem smartly. For international publication at least two authors must take undertaking that content is not plagiarized (Nushi, 2017). With the popularity of internet use the published material is made accessible to all and this has raised the chances of plagiarism (Vassallo, 2018).

Only way to avoid plagiarism from internet sources is to check it through plagiarism processors, some of these are as follows;

Digital Tools	Functions of softwares for word processors.
PDS: Plagiarism detection system	It shows similarity index of content in paraphrasing, parts of speech, Grammer and structure of the content
NLP: Natural Language processor	It identifies detailed plagiarism analysis of fragments in detail
PAN system	It provides data on the annual basis
Turnitin Software	It is functional since 1998. Now it has gained capacity to check plagiarism though internet, Chat GPT and artificial intelligence.

(Vani & Gupta, 2018).

Plagiarism and Second language Students

Researcher interviewed and examined two groups of the students with English as second language. The researcher guided one group in class rooms. The group gone through the language practice. He found that one group showed less plagiarism who was engaged practice workshops of grammar, paraphrasing, punctuation and other relevant semantic exercises (Bethany, 2016). Academic writing “art of writing without plagiarism” (Nness, 2018).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design

Research design for the present study is Quantitative Research Survey Design.

Objectives of the study

The researcher has following objectives

1. To explore the causes of the Plagiarism in the light of university plagiarism policy.
2. To know plagiarism awareness guidelines provided to university students.
3. To examine reasons methods to avoid plagiarism.
4. To develop framework form academic writing

Research Questions

Here in this study following four questions are to be answered.

1. Do the students Know about plagiarism issue?
2. Are the students learning guidelines to avoid plagiarism?
3. Why the students adopt plagiarism culture?
4. Do the students know academic writing skills.

Population

The population belonged to M.Phil students Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan, Institute of Southern Punjab Multan, Women University, Allama Iqbal University Multan (Students form Multan city only) and NCBA &E.

Sampling technique

A sample of 45 M.Phil. students were taken through convenient sampling taking 9 students from each university. Questionnaire was distributed to these students through direct meeting with them, by e-mail, by Whats App. only 43 Responses of questionnaire were received.

Data collection Tool

Questionnaire comprising of 20 items was developed from literature review by the researcher after validation from the relevant experts was distributed to these students through direct meeting with them, by e-mail, by Whats App. And but only 43 Responses of questionnaire were received.

Data collection and Data analysis

A Questionnaire consisting of 20 items was distributed to the M. Phil scholars of public and Private universities. The participants were informed that researcher need to have their opinion about plagiarism awareness and guidelines according to which they were asked to submit their write up in the form of assignment, Review or Term paper. They were also told that the name of department and student name would be kept confidential and will be used only for the research purpose.

The collected data was analysed, and scored based on the presence of the following Themes 1. Existence of the plagiarism 2. Defining the plagiarism 3. Directing the plagiarism 4. Guidelines about the plagiarism 5. Consequences of the plagiarism.

Mean score was calculated for each statement. Then each statement was analysed and compared to level of decision which was taken 3.0

DATA ANALYSIS

The data was collected form and analysed on the 5-point Likert scale the response from student . The responses bear the weightage as under

Scale: 1 = Not at all Scale 2 = Little extent Scale 3 = Some extent Scale 4 = Moderate extent Scale 5 = Great extent . Here the level of agreement to each statement was 3.0 and data is tabulated by calculating frequencies, percentages and mean score of each item.

Mean was calculated by using formula

$$Mean = \frac{5X GE(f) + 4X ME(f) + 3X SE(f) + 2X LE(f) + 1X NA}{Total\ Number\ of\ respondents}$$

Where

Symbol Used	frequency of students agreed to
GE(f)	Greater Extent
ME(f)	Moderate Extent
SE(f)	Some Extent
LE(f)	little Extent
NA(f)	Not at all
ME(f)	Moderate Extent

Statement /Theme	Frequencies' Level of agreement					Mean
	Not at All	Little Extent	Some Extent	Moderate Extent	Great Extent	
01.Student information regarding Plagiarism Percentages	0 0 %	6 14%	11 26%	12 28%	14 33%	3.79
02. Concept of academic writing Percentages	1 2 %	8 19%	14 33%	14 33%	6 14%	3.37
03.APA Manual awareness Percentages	1 2 %	12 28 %	8 19 %	15 35 %	7 16 %	3.34
04.In text copying Percentages	16 37 %	1 2%	4 9%	12 28%	10 23%	2.98
05.Experience of Plagiarism workshops Percentages	2 5%	0 0%	2 5%	1 2%	38 88%	4.69
06.Clear plagiarism instructions from teachers Percentages	12 28%	1 2%	10 23%	7 16%	13 30%	3.19
07 . Unintentional copying Percentages	4 9%	3 7%	14 33%	18 42%	4 9%	3.34
08.Copying with out acknowledgement is bad practice Percentages	8 19%	5 12%	8 19%	5 12%	17 39%	3.41

09.University students have developed copy-paste culture	8	3	8	9	15	3.47
Percentages	19%	7%	19%	21%	35%	
10.plagiarism check facility	16	0		10	17	3.03
Percentages	37%	0%	0%	23%	40%	
11.Plagarism culture is the result of heavy work load and shortage of time	5	9	12	4	13	3.03
Percentages	12%	21%	28 %	9%	30%	
12.Weak concepts of English language	6	0	22	11	4	3.16
Percentages	14%	0%	51%	26%	9%	
13.Got training of ethical and academic writing	4	0	18	17	4	3.40
Percentages	9%	0%	42%	40%	9%	
14.Penalizing students create stress	14	06	10	12	1	2.53
Percentages	33%	14%	23%	28%	2%	
15. citation and referencing original source	11	3	12	2	15	3.16
	26%	7%	28%	5%	35%	
16. weak summarizing skill	3	5	10	23	2	3.37
Percentages	7%	12%	23%	53%	5%	
17.Slight tolerance for coping	6	2	3	22	10	3.65
Percentages	14%	5%	7%	51%	23%	
18.Coping full text idea	3	11	10	8	11	3.30
Percentages	7%	26%	23%	19%	26%	
19. Proper Citation skill	19	12	6	4	2	2.02
Percentages	44 %	28%	14%	9%	5%	
20.Written plagiarism document availability to student.	28	0	4	7	4	2.04
Percentages	65%	0%	9%	16%	9%	

(Learning, 2010)

The Above table statement “I have proper Knowledge of the term Plagiarism”, clearly explores that 0 % students showed no agreement on the statement,

14 % were agreed to little extent , 26 % students agreed to some extent , 28 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 33 % students showed tendency to great extent . The level of Decision was 3.0 , Here mean score 3.79 is Greater than the Level of agreement.

statement “I know the meaning of the term Academic writing.”, clearly explores that 2 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 19 % were agreed to little extent , 33 % students agreed to some extent , 33 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 14 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of Decision was 3.0 , Here mean score 3.37 Greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “Students must follow APA style of referencing in writing assignment.”, clearly explores that 2 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 28 %were agreed to little extent , 19 % students agreed to some extent , 35 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 16 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0 , Here mean score 3.34 is Greater than the Level of agreement. Sstatement “Copying with reference is not plagiarism”, clearly

explores that 37 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 2 %were agreed to little extent , 9 % students agreed to some extent , 28 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 23 % students showed tendency to great extent . The level of agreement was 3.0 , Here mean score 2.98 is less than the Level of agreement. Statement “Students should join online trainings of plagiarism.”, clearly explores that 5 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 0 %were agreed to little extent , 5 % students agreed to some extent , 2 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 88 % students showed tendency to great extent. . The level of agreement was 3.0, Here mean score is 4.69 greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “University teachers have given me clear directions about plagiarism”, clearly explores that 28 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 2 %were agreed to little extent , 23 % students agreed to some extent , 16 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 30 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0, Here means score 3.19 Greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “Sometimes I copy submit the work done by my fellows”, clearly explores that 9 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 7 %were agreed to little extent , 33 % students agreed to some extent ,42 % students agreed to

moderate extent, and 9 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0, Here means score 3.02 is Greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “Plagiarism is a very bad activity”, clearly explores that 19 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 12 % were agreed to little extent , 19 % students agreed to some extent , 12 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 39 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0, Here means score 3.41 Greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “I copy from other assignments as all do the same practice.”, clearly explores that 19 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 7 % were agreed to little extent , 19% students agreed to some extent , 21 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 35 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0, Here mean score 3.47 Greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “My teachers check plagiarism before final submission of the assignment.”, clearly explores that 37 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 0 % were agreed to little extent , 0 % students agreed to some extent , 23 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 40 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0 , Here mean score 3.03 Is greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “Plagiarism is not bad if time is short and work load is very heavy.”, clearly explores that 12 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 21 % were agreed to little extent , 28 % students agreed to some extent , 9 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 30 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0 , Here mean score 3.03 Is greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “My grammar and summarizing skill in English is very good”, clearly explores that 14 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 0 % were agreed to little extent , 51 % students agreed to some extent , 26 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 9 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0 , Here mean score 3.16 is greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “I have done a lot of practice of academic writing”, clearly explores that 9 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 0 % were agreed to

little extent , 42 % students agreed to some extent , 40 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 9 % students showed tendency to great extent.. The level of agreement was 3.0 , Here mean score 3.40 is Greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “There should be no punishment for plagiarism”, clearly explores that 33 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 14 % were agreed to little extent , 23 % students agreed to some extent , 28 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 2 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0 , Here mean score 2.53 is less than the Level of agreement.

Statement “I do a lot of in-text referencing”, clearly explores that 26 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 7 % were agreed to little extent , 28% students agreed to some extent , 5 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 35 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0 , Here mean score 3.16 is Greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “I feel difficulty in paraphrasing.”, clearly explores that 7 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 12 % were agreed to little extent , 23 % students agreed to some extent , 53 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 5 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0 , Here mean score 3.37 is Greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “I feel plagiarism is not intellectual theft”, clearly explores that 14 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 5 % were agreed to little extent , 7 % students agreed to some extent , 51 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 23 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0 , Here mean score 3.65 Greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “Word to word copying from source is sharing of knowledge”, clearly explores that 7 % students showed no agreement on the statement, 26 % were agreed to little extent , 23 % students agreed to some extent , 19 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 26 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0 , Here mean score 3.30 Greater than the Level of agreement. Statement “When using quotation marks page number is not needed in the citation.”, clearly explores that 44 % students showed no agreement on the statement,

28 %were agreed to little extent , 14 % students agreed to some extent , 9 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 5 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0 , Here mean score 2.02 less than the Level of agreement. Statement “I received no written document containing guidelines about plagiarism form university.”, clearly explores that 65 %

students showed no agreement on the statement, 0 %were agreed to little extent , 9 % students agreed to some extent ,16 % students agreed to moderate extent, and 9 % students showed tendency to great extent. The level of agreement was 3.0 , Here mean score 2.04 less than the Level of agreement.

It is clear from above graph that level of agreement was highest for statement 05 and mean score for statement 04,14 and 20 remained below the decision mean.

Research Findings

- 1) The students are aware of the term Plagiarism.
- 2) The students know meaning of the term Academic writing.
- 3) Students have tendency to follow APA style of referencing in writing assignment.
- 4) Students do not agree to statement, Copying with reference is not plagiarism .
- 5) Students need to join online trainings of plagiarism. .
- 6) Students agree to some extent the University teachers have given them clear directions about plagiarism.
- 7)

- 8) Some respondents agreed that they sometimes copy submit the work done by their fellows.
- 9) Majority of the respondents believe that Plagiarism is a very bad activity.
- 10) Respondents agreed that they copy from other assignments as all do the same practice.
- 11) Respondents believe that their teachers teachers check plagiarism before final submission of the assignment.
- 12) Some students do not consider Plagiarism bad if time is short and work load is very heavy.
- 13) Most of the students are of the view that their grammar skills are up to the satisfactory level.
- 14) Respondents are of the view that they have learnt academic writing to some extent.
- 15) As plagiarism is misconduct respondents say that person should be penalized if found in plagiarism.

- 16) Students have a moderate practice of in-text references.
- 17) As English is not the native language so students feel difficulty in paraphrasing.
- 18) Respondents are clear that plagiarism is intellectual theft.
- 19) Word to word comes in the domain of plagiarism.
- 20) use of quotation marks in referencing was not clear to students.
- 21) Most of the respondents did not receive plagiarism guidelines from their university.

Conclusions

1. Majority of the students know about the term plagiarism, few are not clear about it.
2. Most of the students agree that they are getting proper guidelines from their university teacher about plagiarism.
3. The students adopt plagiarism culture to a very small extent. They do so due to less academic writing, poor language skills, shortage of time, lack of paraphrasing and summarising skills, Lack of in-text referencing, weak citation, less use of citation software's and insufficient literature review.
4. Very small number of Students know about academic writing skills.

Suggestions

1. Booklets on Plagiarism are available at HEC website these must be included in the teaching content i.e syllabus so than students may learn it during course work.
2. University plagiarism policy, must be inculcated to the students with direct and on-line courses, Seminars, conferences, student's debates and sessions with the experienced faculty members must be made to generate awareness about plagiarism.
3. Academic writing practice sessions must be arranged on regular basis to improve poor language skills.
4. Students must devote ample time for literature review. This will improve their paraphrasing skills, summarising skills, Lack of in-text referencing and weak citation.

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